

Literary Voice

A Peer Reviewed Journal of English Studies

U.G.C. Care Group II Journal

ISSN 2277-4521 (Print) ISSN 2583-8199 (Online)

Indexed with Web of Science ESCI, Cosmos, ESJI, I2OR, CiteFactor, InfoBase

Number 21 Volume 1 September 2023

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Lenses of "Personal" and "Political" Language in Herta Muller's Prose

Dr. Shaleen Kumar Singh*

Abstract

Herta Müller, a Romanian-German author and Nobel laureate in literature, is known for her powerful and distinctive voice in Germany and Romania. Her early life, impacted by Nicolae Ceaușescu's communist dictatorship, eventually shaped her writings. Herta Muller's prose and fictional works are characterized by a unique combination of realism and surrealism and transport the readers to a world where personal and political problems are tangled, and the line between reality and imagination gets hazy. The fictional works of Herta Muller delve into the struggles of the common man surviving under repressive regimes, the fear and surveillance that permeate their daily life, and the profound effects of censorship and repression on personal and collective identities. She frequently paints marginalized and suppressed characters who reflect the broader social and political contexts in which they live. Her literary works, specially her prose works evoke a vivid sense of intimacy with the characters, thus making readers privy to their vulnerabilities, aspirations and traumas. This paper will scrutinize how her few prominent essays like "Always the Same Snow and Always the Same Uncle," "In Every Language There are Other Eyes," and "Christina and Her Double" address the vulnerability of individuals suffering from oppression and persecution, and examine Muller's experiences as a German-speaking ethnic minority, and explore the relationship between language perception and symbolism. It will also highlight the beauty and depth that language diversity adds to our understanding of the world. In her literary prose, she meticulously explores how language can be manipulated and used as a tool of censorship, propaganda, and control. Besides, her works portray the struggle of individuals to communicate their experiences, feelings and thoughts under oppressive conditions.

Keywords: Prose, understanding, language, political oppression, fear, cultural identity.

Herta Müller is a Romanian-German author and Nobel laureate in literature. In the literary arena, she is known as a powerful and distinctive voice in Germany and Romania. Born on August 17, 1953, in Nitzkydorf, a German-speaking village in Romania, the formative years of Müller were shaped by the oppressive regime of Nicolae Ceaușescu's communist dictatorship. This turbulent upbringing significantly impacted her writing, imbuing her prose with poignant themes of political oppression, identity, memory, and the indomitable human spirit. Her works particularly explore the effects of repression and dictatorship on individuals, families, and communities, highlighting the pervasive fear, surveillance, and control that permeates every aspect of life. The feeling of exile and displacement remains a persistent theme in her fiction as many of her characters find themselves physically or emotionally removed from their homeland, experiencing a sense of alienation and loss of belonging. Their ability to persevere, adapt, and find strength to weather the tough and extreme challenges, is a recurring motif. In this regard the following observations are quite pertinent:

Herta Müller's literary works address an individual's vulnerability under oppression and persecution. Her works are rooted in her experiences as one of Romania's

German-speaking ethnic minority. Müller describes life under Ceaușescu's regime—how dictatorship breeds fear and alienation that stays in an individual's mind. Innovatively and with linguistic precision, she evokes images from the past.

Müller's literary works are largely prosaic, although she also writes poetry. (Herta)

The prose works of Herta Muller are acknowledged for their poetic strength and skilled use of language. Her fiction includes a one-of-a-kind mix of realism and surrealism as it transports the readers to a world in which personal and political problems are tangled, and the line that separates reality from imagination becomes progressively blurred. She creates haunting and evocative images of individuals who have confronted the harsh realities of oppression and brutality and the traumatic impact these had exerted on their lives.

The linguistic virtuosity exhibited by Herta Muller is an extraordinary, striking, and enduring feature as is manifest in her frequent use of linguistic playfulness and inventive expressions of the written word. Being the bilingual writer - German and Romanian – she has added a new dimension to the art of storytelling and essayed a deeper analysis of varied themes relating to migration, cultural identity and communication.

The literary approach of Herta Müller is to explore identity through the use of Romanian words in her works in German and English language writing that mirrors her deep faith in the richness and intricacy of human experiences. It creates a linguistic dissonance that reflects Muller's experience in a country where she is not fully accepted. She admits that proper understanding requires probing beyond superficial descriptions and embracing the complexity that emerges at the intersection of cultures and languages. As Doris Mironescu critically observes:

Müller sees identity as something irreducible to clichés, a complicated construction that reveals its complexity by the obvious fact that it is formed at the intersection of cultures and languages. And the Romanian words that Müller evokes in her recollections are part of complex experiences that cannot be summarized but only alluded to in dense symbols that require long narrations in order to unfold their rich array of significations. (Mironescu)

Müller's prose transcends the boundaries of traditional storytelling, and is a relentless search for truth and an unflinching examination of the human condition that has suffered under an oppressive regime. The literary works of Muller encounter the gloomiest aspects of totalitarian rule and expose the psychological toll of life beneath the constant surveillance and fear. Despite the darkness that informs her literary works, we witness an unwavering resilience in her characters who assert their compassion, sympathy, and morality in the face of degrading and dehumanizing conditions. Her notable poetry and essays include, *Hunger and Silk*, "The King Bows and Kills," "Always the Same Snow and Always the Same Uncle" (Kuiper).

The present paper is based on the language and words employed by the author and the language and words used by the people in her *oeuvre*. Muller believes that things become "something else" at first when we look at them and later when we start to "describe" them through our "words" (Muller, 1). The author adds, "If you want to be precise in your description, you have to find something completely different within the sentence to allow you to be precise" (Muller 1). The author proposes an interesting approach to attain precision in the description through language. One may use a metaphorical or indirect method to communicate one's ideas accurately and precisely.

The author advocates inserting imaginative language to convey deeper layers of meaning, and develop a more nuanced understanding of the subject one intends to share. Muller emphasizes the potency of human imagination in carving the notions and reactions of a human being. According to Muller, imagination can magnify the emotional impact of the perceived threads. It often surpasses the effect of actual dangers in our lives. The following insightful passage suggests analytically that our fears are not solely based on reality, though they heavily influence our mental constructs:

These vagabond qualities that turned one object into another were unpredictable. They distorted one's perception in the blink of an eye, made of it what they wished. Every thin branch swimming in the water resembled a water snake. Because of my constant fear of snakes, I have been afraid of water. Not out of fear of drowning, but out of fear of snake wood, I never learned to swim for fear of scrawny, swimming branches. The imagined snakes had a more powerful effect than real ones could have; they were in my thoughts whenever I saw the river (Muller 2).

The author challenges the conventional idea of language as a reliable tool for drawing a valid and reliable image of reality. Expressing a deep sense of skepticism towards language and laying down the foundational doubt in the ability of a language to accurately convey the meaning, the author points out the inherent ambiguities and gaps in the structure. Highlighting the illusive nature of language, the author avers:

I don't trust language. At best, I know from my own experience that, to be precise, it must always take something that doesn't belong to it. I have no idea why verbal images are so light-fingered, why the most valid comparison steals qualities it's not entitled to. The surprise comes about only through invention, and time and again, it proves true that one gets close to the truth only with the invented surprise in the sentence. Only when one perception steals from another, one object seizes and uses the substance of another - only when that which is impossible in real life has become plausible in the sentence can the sentence hold its own before reality (Muller 3-4).

In an essay, "In Every Language, There Are Eyes," the author reflects on the language's simplicity and directness, the absence of abstract thinking, and the dominating presence of routine instinctive actions. She highlights a child's perspective where the language the village people employ, is straightforward and literal. The author presents a nostalgic reflection on the language and life of villagers seen through a child's eyes and recalls when language and reality were in perfect harmony and an immediate connection between words and the objects they represented. One may observe this idea in the following text:

In the language of the village so it seemed to me as a child-the words of all those around me lay directly on the things they denoted. Things were called just as they were, and they were just as they were called. An agreement concluded for all time. For most people, there were no gaps that allowed them to glimpse between the word and the object and stare into nothingness as if sliding out of one's skin into the void (Muller 15).

Herta Muller delves deep into the intricate relationship between the loss of language, silence, and work arising in a labour-intensive society or environment. She also suggests that the act of working is instrumental in the preservation of language and knowledge. When human beings are engaged in labour, their bodies and minds are occupied with the physical demands of the assigned tasks. At this stage, words usually

become unnecessary and secondary. However, when the work ceases and the silence lingers, a fear arises that the individuals might lose their linguistic abilities over time because language always requires continual practice and use to remain alive. Exemplifying the essence of human experience with specific context and environment, Herta Muller observes:

Words only accompanied work when several people were engaged in a task, and one was dependent on the actions of another. But even then, that wasn't always the case. The heaviest work, such as carrying sacks, digging, hoeing, scything, was a school of silence. The body was under too much strain to waste energy on speech. Twenty or thirty people could remain silent for hours on end. Sometimes I thought, as I watched, that I was learning what happens when people forget how to speak. Once they cease toiling, they will have forgotten every single word. (Muller 16)

In her famous essay, "In Every Language There Are Other Eyes," the author metaphorically expresses the different perspectives and ways of looking at things relating to the speaker's longing for understanding and connecting it with others. In this connection, Herta Muller contemplatively reflects on the effects of reading and writing books. She points out that "reading books or even writing them' does not provide relief. However, their value lies in the frequent availability of passages that evoke a silent disconnection in the head" (Muller 28). Dealing with the transformative power of literature, the author continues to refer to this disconnection and pinpoints the movements when the reader's thoughts are drawn to a place, triggering a deeper understanding or emotional response:

Reading books or even writing them brings no relief. If I have to explain why I find one book rigorous and another shallow, I can only point to the frequency of passages that bring forth a disconnection in the head, passages that draw my thoughts straight to places where no words can survive. The more frequently these passages occur in the text, the more rigorous the book; the sparser they are, the shallower the text. (Muller 28)

Muller also discusses the distinction between prose and poetry and states that both forms of writing share the exact requirement of depth and density. However, the prose contains a more extended form and is rendered differently. Highlighting the unique power of poetry to evoke a vast and immersive experience beyond the literal meaning of its words which weave together lines that interact and overlap with each other and finally create new spaces and depths of meaning, Muller alludes to interview of Bruno Ganz, a frequent performer of poetry, and remarks:

With poetry, it's possible for one line to lay bare a vast space beyond the sense conveyed by the words. In a strange way, it crosses over itself with the next line; new spaces keep opening up, not like a presentation of the evidence in linear prose. There it's a question of shifts, with verticals and strange movements. For me, poetry is to be found in a large space, enveloped with air. There is always more meaning, always more movement than is expressed in words. (Muller 29)

Furthermore, Muller adds that the quality of a well-crafted sentence should be present in both prose and poetry. She suggests that a powerful sentence can transcend the boundary lines of poetry and prose and can effectively blur the lines of prose and poetry forms of writing. Analyzing the distinction between good poetry and prose, she observes:

A good prose sentence is often praised for being lyrical. Perhaps because it stands on

its own, it resembles only a good sentence in poetry: a and not flat one. It's simply a case of two good sentences resembling each other. The sentence: 'When the birds die, they drift belly up in the wind' in Antunes's prose is self-evident. It only sounds like good poetry because it is also good prose." (Muller 38)

Muller also reflects on her experience of language acquisition and the significance of her surrounding. According to her, people listen attentively to the language spoken around them and absorb it when verbal communication fails, "When your surroundings only speak what you can't speak, you listen to the language along with the whole region. And if you stay long enough the time in the region learns the language for you. That was my experience; the head had no idea how it happened" (Muller 32). She also emphasizes the importance of listening in language learning, a foundation for effective communication. When the speaker immerses in the language and culture, their speaking ability naturally develops. Giving a contrast between the two languages, Muller says, "But listening is a preparation for speaking. One day the mouth began to speak of its own accord. Then Rumanian was like my own language. In contrast to German, the words were astonished when I found myself involuntarily comparing them with my German words" (Muller 32). Muller analyses language's wide variety and nuances by describing the wind and different dialects. She draws attention to how the high German and Romanian village dialect has unique ways of expressing the wind's movement, sound, and impact.

In the village dialect, we say: the wind GOES. In the High German spoken in school, we say: the wind WAILS. And to my seven-year-old ears, it sounded as if the wind had hurt itself. In Rumanian we say: the wind HITS, *vintul bate*. You could hear the sound of movement as you said 'hits', so the wind didn't hurt itself but others. The wind ceasing is as different as the wind wailing. In German, we say: the wind has lain down - flat and horizontal. In Rumanian, we say: the wind has STOOD STILL, virtual a stat, steep and vertical. The example of the wind is just one of the constant shifts that occur between languages. Almost every sentence is a different glance. Rumanian saw the world as differently as its words were different. It was also differently woven into the net of grammar. (Muller 33)

Muller explores the intricate interplay between language perception and symbolism of a lily as seen through the critical lens of two different languages, German and Romanian. The author implies that knowing and appreciating other languages enriches one's perception of the world. For instance, lily becomes a multifaceted symbol. It opens multiple layers of meaning and invites the reader to see more than a single perspective can give us. It also enhances and showcases the beauty and depth that language diversity can add to our understanding of the object of this world. She adds:

What does the lily become in two languages that are running side by side? A woman's nose in a man's face, a long, greenish palate, or a white glove or collar. Does it smell of coming and going or of staying put? Through the meeting of two aspects of the lily, the closed lily of the two languages has become a mysterious never-ending event. An ambiguous lily remains restless in the head and is always saying something unexpected about itself and the world. You can see more in it than in the one-language lily. (Muller 33)

Pinpointing the profound relationship with the mother tongue and the challenges that arise when one navigates to a new language, the author remarks that we all trust the

“familiarity” and solidity of the mother tongue as it flows naturally; from our mouths without conscious effort. It is an intrinsic part of our self, akin to our skin. Despite all such truths, this comforting connection turns vulnerable when others belittle, disregard or forbid its use. However, the unique characteristic of the mother tongue gets visible through its exposure to other languages. The encounter with other languages may boost and strengthen the relationship with one's mother tongue by fostering a sense of solid connection and a relaxed form of love. One gains a new perspective and understanding of idiosyncracies of one's mother tongue when a person holds one's language up to the scrutiny of another language. When the individuals examine and evaluate the intricacies and unique features of their mother tongue in comparison to a different language, they experience a profound shift in how they perceive and comprehend linguistic intricacies.

By subjecting their language to the scrutiny of another, individuals uncover subtle nuances, peculiarities, and distinct qualities that might have previously gone unnoticed. This process fosters a heightened awareness of the idiosyncrasies present within their native language. As a result, individuals not only become more attuned to the mechanics of their own language but also gain an enriched perspective on how language functions in general. The act of juxtaposing languages encourages a deeper understanding of the ways in which grammar, syntax, vocabulary, and cultural connotations shape communication. It can lead to a more profound appreciation for the beauty and complexity inherent in both the mother tongue and the language being compared. This exploration can also highlight the limitations and strengths of each language in conveying certain concepts, emotions, and ideas.

Through this process, one may appreciate one's nuances and distinctiveness, thereby deepening one's bond with one's native language. The author says rightly, “No mother tongue suffers when its randomness becomes apparent in the seeing of other languages. On the contrary, holding one's language up to the eyes of another leads to a solid relationship, a relaxed kind of love. I didn't love Mother better because it's the most familiar” (Muller 35). Muller explores the profound impact of the repressive regime on language and communication. According to Muller, words collapse under the weight of existential turmoil when life starts searching its meaning. Dictatorships often exploit language and manipulate words to control and suppress the truth.

While discussing the metaphorical conceptualization of injurious and injured language employed by Herta Müller, the power of language to harm and silence, to underscore the importance of preserving freedom of expression and the complexities of communication under such circumstances, Pavlo Shopin, a critic of Herta Muller observes:

In the most extreme scenario, the injury inflicted upon language metaphorically kills it and silences the speaker, where silence is construed as a symptom of a lethal injury to language. While injurious language can bring about the death of a human being, injury is conceptualized by Müller as a possible factor in the metaphorical death of language, leading to silence. Ultimately, the metaphorical conceptualization of injurious and injured language allows Herta Müller to convey to the reader the dangers and limitations of art and communication in the condition of oppression. (Shopin)

Herta Muller refers to her first book titled *Nadirs Niederungen* (originally published in 1982) which was set in Banat Swabian village. The Romanian publisher of this

book censored the word “SUITCASE” and other content of it. The censors of the book were afraid that the word “SUITCASE” would suggest the desire to leave the country, which was a crime under the communist regime at the time. Such an act of censorship mirrors an attempt to silence specific vital topics. Through censorship of words and concepts, the dictatorship aims to blindfold people's understanding of language and hinder them from expressing and comprehending certain truths. Here, prescribed language enforcement perpetuates the malevolence of oppressive regimes and contributes to the degradation of society and decline in intellectual and emotional freedom. Language manipulation and censorships by the dictatorship hinder communication, suppress the truth and create an atmosphere of oppression and fear.

To sum up, language is not a neutral entity but an integral part of power dynamics. If we pore over the pages of history and look beyond the horizon of culture, we find that language is entwined with politics as a tool for communication or as a means of persuasion and influence. Language remains interwind with the actions and intentions of the people to use it so that it can be influential and ethical. In every linguistic expression, there are some underlined perspectives. The way people communicate one another mirrors their value system and belief system. Therefore, the phrase 'other eyes' seems apt when we go through the following passage:

Nowhere and at no time was or is language a non-political preserve; it cannot be separated from what one person does to another. It always lives in the individual case. Every time we must listen to what its intentions are. Inseparable from action, it becomes legitimate or unacceptable, beautiful or ugly; you could also say: good or evil. In every language, in every way of speaking, there are other eyes. (Muller 46-47)

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